

Covid-19 infectiOn aNd medicineS In pregGNancy

Deliverable 6: Description and characterization of the data sources to be included in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis

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List of abbreviations

ACOG	American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists
ARDS	Acute respiratory distress syndrome
ARS	Agenzia Regionale di Sanita' della Toscana
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical
BMI	Body Mass Index
CAMCCO	Canadian Mother-Child Cohort
CAN-AIM	CANadian Network for Advanced Interdisciplinary Methods for comparative effectiveness research
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CI	Confidence interval
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
CONSIGN	Covid-19 infectiOn aNd medicineS In pregGNancy
DP	Data Provider
DAP	Data Access Provider
DNA	Desoxyribonucleic acid
DSEN	Drug Safety and Effectiveness Network
ECMO	Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EMR	Electronic Medical Records
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU PAS	The European Union electronic Register of Post-Authorisation Studies
FICF	Catalan Institute of Pharmacology Foundation
FISABIO-HSRU	Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region - Health Services Research Unit
GP	General Practitioner
IACS	Instituto Aragones de Ciencias de la Salud
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
LMP	Last menstrual period
mRNA	messenger Ribonucleic acid
NAAT	Nucleic Acid Amplification Test
NHS	National Health Service
ODHSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
QC	Quality Control
SAIL	Secure Anonymized Information Linkage
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
SARS-CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2
UiO	University of Oslo

Executive summary

This document describes the data sources to be included in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis that aims to assess medicine use and their effects on the management of COVID-19 in pregnancy.

The key objectives of CONSIGN-International are to describe and estimate:

- 1) Use of medicines to treat COVID-19 infection in pregnancy
- 2) The impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy and neonatal outcomes
- 3) Effects of medicines used to treat COVID-19 infection in pregnancy on pregnancy, perinatal and neonatal outcomes

In chapter 1, we describe the current status of the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis, including the rationale and a summary of the steps and procedures conducted so far.

In chapter 2, we describe the data sources to be included in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis.

Paragraph 2.1 lists the data sources based on the secondary use of health care data, while paragraph 2.2 gives an overview of the data sources based on primary data collection from health clinics.

In chapter 3, we elaborate on the proposed approaches and discuss the next steps of the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis.

1. Current status of the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis

The Covid-19 infectiOn aNd medicineS In pregGNancy (CONSIGN) project implements various analyses to estimate the use of medicines and their effects in COVID-19 affected pregnancies to guide decision-making by EMA and its committees about vaccine indications, vaccination policies, and treatment options for COVID-19 disease and associated complications. CONSIGN builds on ongoing primary data collections in the EU initiated COVI-PREG and INOSS networks, and secondary use of data based on the IMI-funded ConcePTION tools and network¹. The ultimate goal of this work is to create a global and sustainable infrastructure for prospective benefit-risk monitoring of treatments in pregnancy beyond those used in COVID-19 as part of the CONSIGN work.

1.1. Work in 2021

In December 2020, CONSIGN delivered a report that made an inventory of all international initiatives investigating the impact of COVID-19 on pregnancies, during this inventory many opportunities for international collaboration were identified.² These were explored with the European Medicines Agency in different meetings of ICMRA members and beyond.

CONSIGN also delivered a protocol for electronic health record data analysis which was registered in the EU PAS register (EUPAS39438) and analysis plans for the COVI-PREG and INOSS data collections. Several interim analyses and a final analysis of the COVI-PREG data were conducted. The reports and executive summary are available on the CONSIGN Zenodo community space.^{3,4}

1.2. What we have learned so far

Based on the final analysis of COVI-PREG data⁴, interim analysis from CONSIGN³, publications from some of the INOSS members^{5,6,7} and international literature⁸, we know that use of medicines specific for COVID-19 in pregnant women is infrequent, highly correlated with the severity of COVID-19 disease and changing over time. We also know that pregnant women have not been included in the majority of clinical trials for COVID-19 medicines and vaccines, which leaves an important gap in knowledge.

A recent review by the CONSIGN research team, of the recommendations on medicines used in COVID-19 affected women, shows there are a lot of different recommendations across international organizations and countries over time.^{9,10,11,12,13,14,15} This is underlining the fact that evidence is changing, regarding the ever-evolving literature and the emergence of new variants corresponding to the different waves of the pandemic.

Many other organizations and initiatives are collecting information on COVID-19 in pregnancy. Based on our review and to our best knowledge, the only initiative focusing on the impact of medicines in COVID-19 affected pregnancies is CONSIGN; all other studies appear to be focusing on the solely impact of COVID-19 disease. Therefore, uniting efforts and international collaboration to assess the impact of COVID-19 medicines in pregnant women are required.

1.3. Methods and criteria for collaboration

Based on the identified initiatives in the CONSIGN deliverable 2b², EMA and CONSIGN leadership reached out to these initiatives for international collaboration in medicine use and their effects on the management of COVID-19 in pregnancy, the so-called CONSIGN-International.

Collaboration of CONSIGN with other data sources will provide more knowledge on the treatments used and their effects on pregnancy outcomes. The key objectives of CONSIGN-International are to assess and estimate:

- 1) Use of medicines to treat COVID-19 infection in pregnancy
- 2) Effects of medicines used to treat COVID-19 infection in pregnancy on pregnancy, perinatal and neonatal outcomes

Eligibility criteria for collaboration

To generate valid information on medicine use and the effects of medicines on pregnancy outcomes, we include as potential collaborators all data collections originating from:

- Healthcare databases corresponding to secondary use of administrative and electronic health care data and medical claims data
- Case-based databases including primary data collection from health care facilities and professionals

We do not include self-reported data on pregnancies due to potential bias and misclassification of medicine use. Furthermore, for analysis of EHR data organizations should have the resources to share results and to have implemented the CONSIGN protocol (EUPAS39438) or protocol with similar design and objectives for EHR data in their networks.

Sites were asked to share their analysis plan and provide additional materials, and collaboration meetings were conducted to understand what data was being collected and which protocols were used. During these calls we assessed:

- What is the source population from which they obtain their pregnant women? Is this based on certain settings? Is this all population?
- How do women enter these settings? When will they be eligible to be included in the data collection? Is there a potential for selection bias?
- How do we know the outcomes? How are the pregnancies followed up? What is the potential for loss to follow-up?
- How long is the follow-up time of newborns?
- How is the data on medicines collected? Is this all medicines or restricted to certain settings?

Table 1 describes the initiatives that have been identified and their participation status. Figure 1 visualizes this selection process of data sources in a flowchart. Fifty-six data sources provided by healthcare professionals containing information on pregnant women with COVID-19 were identified. Of these, 13 were based on secondary use of electronic health care data, whereas 43 were case based.

Table 1: Overview of ongoing projects and opportunities for international collaboration by country and type of data collection (updated from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5211395>)²

Continent	Country	Study / network name	Type of data source		Contact via	Approach and decision for collaboration
			Healthcare data	Case based data		
North America	USA	Sentinel	X		FDA/Harvard Pilgrim Health Care Institute	Yes, implementing CONSIGN WP1 protocol
		VSD	X		Shimakaburo, CDC	No, medicines are not in scope
		CDC surveillance (SET-NET)		X	CDC	Yes
		Washington state COVID-19		X	George Washington MA	Yes
		NICHD MFMU		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Canada	CAN-AIM CAMCCO	X		Health Canada	Yes
		CAN-AIM CONCEPTION		X	Health Canada	Yes, but not eligible after reviewing of the protocol (self-reported cases)
		CANCOVID		X	George Washington MA	Yes
South & Middle America	Chile	GESTACOVID		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Colombia	RECOGEST		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Suriname	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
Europe	Netherlands	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Norway	INOSS / U Oslo	X	X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Sweden	INOSS / KI	X	X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Denmark	INOSS/Aarhus	X	X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Germany	GEPARD	X		CONSIGN	Yes
	Italy	INOSS/ARS	X	X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Iceland	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Ireland	ROI-COVID-19		X	CONSIGN	No answer to collaboration proposal
	Finland	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Romania	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
	Slovakia	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes
	Belgium	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes
	France	INOSS (COROPREG) for case-based data /BPE (SNDS) for healthcare data	X	X	CONSIGN	Yes
	UK	INOSS/Swansea	X	X	CONSIGN	Yes
		CPRD			MHRA	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
	Spain	Madrid hospital-based registry		X	George Washington MA	Yes
		FISABIO-HSRU	X		CONSIGN	Yes
Aragon		X		CONSIGN	Yes	
CatOSS			X	CONSIGN	Yes	

		Obs COVID		X	CONSIGN	No answer to collaboration proposal
Africa	Kenya	ANCOV / ARC Kenya		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Mali	CCV		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Uganda	PERICOVID		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Malawi	PERICOVID		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	The Gambia	PERICOVID		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Mozambique	PERICOVID		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Ethiopia	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
	Ghana	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
	South Africa	INOSS		X	CONSIGN	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
Oceania	New Zealand	CHOPAN		X	George Washington MA	Yes
	Australia	CHOPAN		X	George Washington MA	Yes
Asia	China	China Registry		X	George Washington MA	Yes
		Hong Kong registry			George Washington MA	Yes
	India	PREGCOVID		X	CONSIGN	No answer to collaboration proposal
	Japan	COVID-19 & Pregnancy in Japan		X	PDMA	Yes, but no resources for collaboration
	Saudi-Arabia	COVID-19 & Pregnancy in Saudi		X	SFDA	Yes
Multiple continents	COVI-PREG			X	CONSIGN	Yes
	INOSS			X	CONSIGN	Yes
	NICHD global network			X	George Washington MA	Yes
	InterCOVID			X		No answer to collaboration proposal
	OHDSI		X		Talita Duarte Salles	Implemented different types of analysis, not the CONSIGN WP1, new study would be required.

In Figure 2, we show the phases of the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis. Phase 1 of the process identifies and connects with ongoing projects and opportunities for collaboration, sharing data-analysis plan and additional materials, reviewing data sources and agreement for participation. The following chapter will describe the initiatives that agreed to participate in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis based on secondary use of health care data (paragraph 2.1) and based on primary data collection from health clinics (paragraph 2.2).

Figure 1. Flowchart of the data sources selection process

Figure 2. Overview of the progress in CONSIGN-International meta-analysis

2. Organizations that agreed to participate in CONSIGN-International meta-analysis

We summarize the organizations and initiatives that agreed to participate in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis based on two types of data collection, retrospective secondary use of electronic health care data and primary data collected in ongoing registries of SARS-CoV-2 exposed pregnancies, in paragraph 2.1 and 2.2. respectively.

2.1. Secondary use of electronic health care data

Eligible for participation were networks or single data sources with access to population-based electronic health care databases, which can identify pregnancy end and start and can link to medicines and COVID-19 diseases. We ensure that data sources will not be included more than once, as they may be present in multiple networks. The identified networks and data access providers that agreed to participate are listed in Table 2 and elaborated on in the coming paragraphs.

Table 2. Overview participating data sources based on retrospective secondary use of health care data

Study / network name	Country	Catchment area/DAPs	Contact person
CONSIGN WP1 (EMA)	Multiple countries in Europe	AUH (Denmark) SNDS (France) GePaRD (Germany) ARS database (Italy) IACS (Spain) FISABIO-HSRU (Spain) Swansea (UK) KI (Sweden) UiO (Norway)	Dr. Eimir Hurley Dr. Hedvig Marie Egeland Nordeng, Lead of WP1
Sentinel System (USA-FDA and Harvard Pilgrim Health Care Institute)	USA	Across the USA	Mayura Shinde and Jennifer Lyons, Sentinel Leads of project Wei Hua, FDA
CAMCCO (Health Canada)	Canada	Québec Manitoba Alberta Ontario (potentially)	Prof. Dr. Anick Bérard, CAMCCO Lead of project Sasha Bernatsky, CAIN-AIM PI Melissa Kampman and Celline Brasil, Health Canada

2.1.1. ConcePTION CONSIGN WP1 (EMA)

Work package 1 of CONSIGN uses electronic health care registry data. The primary objectives are:

- 1) To estimate the prevalence of medicines used by trimester of pregnancy and compare this among pregnant women with COVID-19, pregnant women without COVID-19, and non-pregnant women with COVID-19.
- 2) To describe severity and clinical outcomes of COVID-19 disease in pregnant women with COVID-19, according to treatments received during pregnancy, and compare these data with those of non-pregnant women of reproductive age with COVID-19.
- 3) To assess and compare the rates of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes in pregnant women with and without COVID-19, using different medicines

Table 3. Overview of data sources to be used for the CONSIGN WP1 analysis

Data source	Area	DAP	Estimated births per year	Type of data source	Diagnose recordings	Medicines	Period over which pregnancies can be identified	Pregnancy start	Pregnancy end	COVID-19 diagnosis
ARS database (ARS)	Italy – Tuscany	ARS	25 000	Record linkage	Hospital	Outpatient Dispensing	Completed and ongoing pregnancies	Date of record minus gestational age / estimated on diagnostic code or period of pregnancy when a procedure is first expected	Date of record / estimated from due date based on estimation of start date	Registry of positive COVID-19 tests (official surveillance system)
Valencia Integrated Database (VID)	Spain – Valencia	FISABIO-HSRU	32 000	Record linkage	GP, specialist Hospital	Outpatient Dispensing & prescriptions	Completed and ongoing pregnancies	Date of LMP / date of delivery minus gestational age / date of delivery minus 40 weeks when newborns weight is 2500 gr or above and through a linear model when weight <2500 gr	Date of delivery or abortion	All PCR or antigen test results are recorded in RedMIVA (Microbiological Surveillance Network of the Valencian Community)
SAIL database (SAIL)	UK – Wales	SWANSEA	33 000	Record linkage	GP, Hospital	Outpatient Prescription	Completed pregnancies only	Date of delivery minus gestational age at birth	Monday of the infant’s week of delivery (to avoid use of identifiable data)	COVID-19 test results dataset available from healthdatagateay.org which include all test results and symptom trackers.
PRECOVID Study and EpiChron Cohort (PRECOVID)	Spain – Aragon	IACS	10 000	Cohort	GP, Hospital	Outpatient Dispensing	Completed and ongoing pregnancies	Date of the LMP	Date of the pregnancy delivery or abortion recorded in primary care or hospital discharge	Registry developed for monitoring the evolution of COVID-19 disease in the region, includes all PCR or antigen test results
Linked national registries (Norway)	Norway	UiO	60 000	Record linkage	GP, Hospital	Outpatient Dispensing	Completed pregnancies only	Date of delivery minus gestational length in days based on US or LMP	Date of delivery	Laboratory confirmed positive test recorded in MSIS (Norwegian surveillance system for communicable diseases)
Linked national registries (Denmark)	Denmark	Aarhus University	60 000	Record linkage	Hospital	Outpatient Dispensing	Completed pregnancies only	Date of delivery – gestational length in days	Date of delivery	Not applicable
Système National des Données de Santé (SNDS)	France	BPE	700 000	Health insurance	Hospital	Out + inpatient Dispensing	Completed pregnancies only	Date estimated from pregnancy algorithm which includes LMP and gestational age	Date of delivery	Inpatient data (PMSI) with ICD10 codes for COVID-19 diagnoses. No laboratory positive test result available.
The German Pharmacoepidemiological Research Database (GePaRD)	Germany	BIPS	150 000	Health insurance	GP, Hospital	Out + inpatient Dispensing	Completed pregnancies only	Estimated delivery date (EDD) – 280 days or date of delivery – median length of pregnancy if no EDD is available.	Date of delivery or abortion	Not applicable
Linked national registries (Sweden)	Sweden	Karolinska Institutet	100 000	Record linkage	Specialists, Hospital	Outpatient Dispensing	Completed pregnancies only	Date of delivery minus gestational length in days based on US or LMP	Date of delivery	All positive PCR test results registered in SmiNet (national patient register) and ICD-10 diagnosis for COVID-19

Data sources

The CONSIGN WP1 study includes data from 9 electronic health registries in 8 European countries (Table 3). Together they comprise 113 million individuals and approximately 1 million pregnancies per year. Data sources include general practice database (e.g., UK, Spain), claims databases (e.g., France, Germany, Italy), and record linkage of demographic data, registers covering primary and secondary care and prescription registries (e.g., Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Italy, Spain).³ Information on pregnancy start and end and COVID-19 diagnosis are provided in Table 3 for the five DAPS who participated in the interim analysis.

Data management and sharing

Data is collected in a distributed manner using the ConcePTION common data model and common analytics developed through the ConcePTION collaboration. ConcePTION is a project funded by the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) and aims to establish a trusted ecosystem that can efficiently, systematically, and in an ethically responsible manner, generate and disseminate reliable evidence-based information regarding the effects of medications used during pregnancy on women and their infants.¹⁶

Data of the different DAPs will be transformed locally to the ConcePTION CDM v2.2 and analyzed using R-scripts that UMC Utrecht generates. To guarantee data quality, ConcePTION data quality indications will also be used. Details are described in the protocol.

2.1.2. Sentinel System (FDA)

Sentinel System comprises health care organizations in the United States, known as Data Partners, that have primarily medical billing information, and in some cases electronic health records. This data is collected routinely with every healthcare encounter and is used to answer FDA's medical product safety questions. Each Data Partner transforms their own data into a standardized common-data model format, runs analyses through parameterized data programs and sends the de-identified results to the Sentinel Operations Center. The Sentinel System's distributed approach maintains patient privacy and data security.¹⁷ The Sentinel Distributed Database has 351.8 million unique patient identifiers spanning from 2000 to 2021 time period. If patients move between health plans, they may have more than one patient identifier. About 230.7 million patients have at least one day of drug and medical coverage. The Sentinel Distributed Database contains 5.1 million linked live birth deliveries with infant records.¹⁸ An algorithm used to identify pregnancies is based on identifying live birth deliveries.¹⁹

Data source

Early in the COVID-19 pandemic, the Sentinel System has provided enhanced data and analytic needs to support FDA's response to the pandemic. New data sources were incorporated in the Sentinel System, and new protocols were developed to evaluate real-world data on the natural history of COVID-19 disease and the utilization of medicines for COVID-19 prevention and treatment. For this, an algorithm based on diagnosis codes was validated to identify patients with COVID-19 in the Sentinel System data sources.^{20,21}

For the Sentinel analyses, they will use the most recently refreshed data from 6 data partners (DPs) participating in the Rapid COVID-19 Sentinel Distributed Database. The database includes 2 claims-based and 4 integrated care delivery systems that include primarily commercially insured populations, with more frequent data updating every 4-6 weeks and standardized quality checks performed. Two of the DPs are national claims-insurers and the other 4 DPs have regional coverage in Colorado, Oregon, Minnesota, and Washington States (Table 4). As of January 2022, approximately 82 million unique patient identifiers are available in the Rapid Sentinel Distributed Database with 33% of members identified from South, 22% from West, 20% from Midwest, and 13% from Northeast regions of United States. More than 44 million patients have at least one day of drug and medical coverage. Information on SARS-CoV-2 diagnostic labs (PCR/NAAT, antigen tests) and data on demographics, enrollment, diagnosis, procedure, and dispensing information is also available.

According to their study protocol on COVID-19 and pregnancy²², Sentinel implemented two aims of the CONSIGN protocol:

- 1) Compare medications used for the treatment of COVID-19 and other medical conditions
- 2) Describe severity and clinical outcomes of COVID-19

Both aims will compare pregnant patients with COVID-19 (aims 1 and 2), pregnant patients without COVID-19 (aim 1), and non-pregnant patients of reproductive age with COVID-19 (aims 1 and 2). Important to note is that the Sentinel system identifies only pregnancies resulting in live birth delivery and pregnancies resulting in other outcomes (e.g., stillbirths, spontaneous abortions, induced abortions) will not be captured.

Data collection

A range of covariates have been outlined in the CONSIGN protocol for describing the maternal clinical characteristics, at-risk conditions, and obstetric complications that may influence the severity of COVID-19 and medication utilization during pregnancy. These covariates will be used for characterization and stratification/adjustment in propensity score matched analyses.

- Demographics: age groups, ethnicity, census bureau regions
- Maternal baseline characteristics: parity, reproductive history, folic acid use, smoking status, educational level, obesity, socio-economic status
- Maternal pre-existing or at-risk medical conditions: cardiovascular diseases, respiratory diseases, diabetes, rheumatic diseases, cancer, mental disorders
- Maternal obstetric conditions: gestational diabetes, gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, assisted reproductive technology, prior pregnancy with stillbirth, SGA, or congenital anomaly
- COVID-19-related health care utilization: supplemental oxygen, high flow oxygen or non-invasive mechanical ventilation, invasive mechanical ventilation or ECMO
- Severity of COVID-19: the World Health Organization proposed categories will be used:
 - Level 1: Any recorded diagnosis
 - Level 2: Hospitalization for COVID-19
 - Level 3: Intensive care unit (ICU) admission in those with COVID-19 related admission
 - Level 4: Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation (ARDS) during a hospitalization for COVID-19
 - Level 5: Death during a hospitalization for COVID-19 (any cause)

They will identify the highest level of COVID-19 severity observed during the specified period of evaluation (pre-pregnancy or trimester periods) in both pregnancies with COVID and non-pregnant cohort with COVID-19.

- Medication Exposure Assessment: medications used for treatment of COVID-19 or other medical conditions will be examined for each study objective:
 - Anticoagulants/platelet inhibitors
 - Antivirals
 - Antibacterials
 - Antimycotics
 - Antimycobacterials
 - Immune sera and globulins
 - Vaccinations
 - Analgesics
 - Psycholeptics
 - Psychoanaleptics
 - Diabetes
 - Corticoosteroids
 - Immunostimulants
 - Immunosuppressants
 - Anti-inflammatory drugs, especially non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
 - Nasal preparations
 - Medicines for obstructive airway disease
 - Cough and cold medications

Coding system

- COVID-19 case definition: COVID-19 will be defined using either COVID-19-related International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) diagnosis codes *or* a positive result of an eligible COVID-19 laboratory test. Eligible laboratory tests include a reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) or other nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT) for SARS-CoV-2 or a SARS-CoV-2 antigen test.
- End and start of pregnancy: Because the date of the last menstrual period (LMP) is not available in the health plan data, the algorithm calculates the length of the pregnancy episode and LMP using ICD-10-CM codes indicative of weeks of gestation, as well as ICD-10-CM codes for pre-term and post-term deliveries in the inpatient care setting. For the purpose of gestational dating, the LMP is used as the start date of pregnancy.
- Medication exposure: Medications will be identified from outpatient pharmacy claims using National Drug Codes (NDC) and from encounter claims data using Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System (HCPCS). The date of dispensing or administration of medication will be used for medication exposure assessment.
- Maternal pre- existing or at- risk medical conditions: ICD-10-CM diagnosis codes recorded in encounter claims or NDC/HCPCS codes recorded in outpatient pharmacy or encounter claims (used as proxies for identification for at-risk medical conditions) will be identified to characterize at-risk groups for developing severe COVID-19. At- risk groups will be created for each of the at-risk medical conditions.

Data management and sharing

The Sentinel System uses fully customizable, parameterizable tools to identify cohorts of interest. Sentinel analytic tools SAS macros and are publicly available for download at the following location: <https://www.sentinelinitiative.org/methods-data-tools/software-packages-toolkits>. They will use the pregnancy tool algorithm and propensity score tools to identify pregnant patients with and without COVID-19 and non-pregnant patients with COVID-19.

2.1.3. CAMCCO (Health Canada)

The Drug Safety and Effectiveness Network (DSEN) is a pan-Canadian network of independent investigators established as a partnership between the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR) and Health Canada. DSEN has the mandate, expertise and capacity to systematically conduct “real-world” drug safety and effectiveness research required by decision makers.^{23 24}

The Canadian Mother-Child Cohort Initiative (CAMCCO), a multi-DSEN team collaboration, with six standardized and harmonized provincial mother-child longitudinal, population-based cohorts (Quebec, Ontario, British Columbia, Manitoba, Saskatchewan, and Alberta) aims to study the impact of prescription drug use during pregnancy and long-term health outcomes in the mother and child.²⁵ CAMCCO cohorts have more than 20 years of longitudinal follow-up for mothers and children (1997-2020, approximately 4,000,000 pregnancies and their children), including important data on the prevalence of medication use during pregnancy and childhood, the prevalence of major malformations, prematurity and low birth weight, and other relevant child and mother outcomes.

The CAMCCO data come from billing databases but also from hospitalization databases and birth certificates. They develop standardized and harmonized tools (CDM/definitions/codes/algorithms) based on the Quebec Pregnancy / Child Cohort (QPC) and the US Sentinel. Using the CDM, crude data can remain in one pre-identified site in each province and the aggregate data are downloaded on the CAMCCO site. This data can be used for meta-analysis or surveillance purposes, and to answer novel research questions, as they are now doing for COVID-19 and pregnancy. Results from a study performed within the Quebec Pregnancy Cohort on COVID-19 repurposed medications were recently published and this methodology will further be used to answer the query on the use of repurposed medicines in pregnancy for COVID-19.²⁶ By following the CONSIGN protocol concerning medication definitions, diagnosis codes and some analyses, they want to answer the same objectives as within CONSIGN. The analyses will include only Quebec, Manitoba, Alberta and potentially Ontario to respect short timelines (Table 5).

Data collection

The variables of interest include:

- COVID-19 diagnosis: identified by diagnostic codes in surveillance systems, health care records and/or laboratory test results.
- Risk factors for COVID-19: trimester of infection, age at the start of pregnancy, obesity, smoking, parity, co-morbidity (e.g., cardiovascular, respiratory, diabetes, rheumatic diseases, cancer, mental disorder), vaccinations (e.g., influenza), timing of pregnancy during the pandemic.

Table 4. Overview of data sources to be used in the Sentinel System for COVID-19 and Pregnancy

Data source	Area	Estimated births per year	Type of data source	Diagnoses recordings	Medicines	Period over which pregnancies can be identified	Pregnancy start	Pregnancy end	COVID-19 diagnosis
Sentinel Distributed Database	USA	Approximately 500,000 live-birth deliveries	Health insurance claims data	Inpatient and outpatient	outpatient	From January 2020 until most recent data refresh	Estimated based on date of live-birth delivery and gestational age codes surrounding delivery date	ICD-10 diagnosis code indicating live-birth delivery	ICD-10 diagnosis code for COVID-19 and/or positive COVID-19 lab test

Table 5. Overview of data sources to be used in CAMCCO for COVID-19 and Pregnancy

Data source	Area	DAP	Estimated births per year	Type of data source	Diagnoses recordings	Medicines	Period over which pregnancies can be identified	Pregnancy start	Pregnancy end	COVID-19 diagnosis
Billing, hospital and birth certificate	Alberta	Edmonton	70000	linked	in/out	Outpatient	1996-12/2021	Algorithm estimating First day of LMP	Clinically detected Spontaneous or planned abortion; or delivery	PCR test
Billing, hospital and birth certificates	Manitoba	Winnipeg	70000	linked	in/out	outpatient	1996-12/2021	Algorithm estimating First day of LMP	Clinically detected Spontaneous or planned abortion; or delivery	PCR test
Billing, hospital, Birth certificate	Quebec	Montreal	100000	linked	in/out	outpatient	1998-05/2020	First day of last LMP	Clinically detected Spontaneous or planned abortion; or delivery	ICD-10
Billing, hospital and birth certificates; linked to EMR at delivery (BORN)	Ontario (?)	Ottawa	100000	linked	in/out	Outpatient and some in-patient collected at delivery	2010-12/2021	First day of LMP (for deliveries); Algorithm to estimate First day of LMP (for spontaneous and planned abortions)	Clinically detected Spontaneous or planned abortion; or delivery	PCR test

- Severity of COVID-19: classified according to WHO scale as follows:
 - Level 1: any recorded diagnosis
 - Level 2: hospitalization for COVID-19 (confirmed or suspected)
 - Level 3: ICU admission in those with COVID-19 related admission
 - Level 4: Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation (ARDS) during hospitalization for COVID-19
 - Level 5: death during hospitalization for COVID-19 (any cause)
- Medications: All medications outpatient/inpatient prescription/dispensing codes (DIN, dosage, duration) will be described by therapeutic class (ATC-level 2) and when sufficient exposures, on an individual drug level (ATC-level 5).
- Hospitalization data: diagnoses during hospitalizations (calendar year), gestational age, procedures, data on delivery/end of pregnancy
- Pregnancy outcomes: congenital anomalies (incl. microcephaly), preterm birth, low birth weight, small for gestational age/ intrauterine growth restriction, spontaneous abortions, stillbirth, type of delivery, induced terminations of pregnancy for fetal anomaly (TOPFA).
- Perinatal/neonatal outcomes: Infection (e.g., SARS-CoV-2 infection), low APGAR score at 5 min, perinatal/neonatal complications, neonatal death

Coding system

The medical service databases (Medical Services file) contain detailed information on all medical services, including physician-based diagnosis and therapeutic procedures, diagnoses coded according to the International Classification of Diseases, ninth and tenth revisions (ICD-9, ICD-10), as well as the date and information on the institutions where the medical procedures were performed. Health care provider characteristics are also included. The Prescription Drug file covers information on all filled prescribed medications, the prescribing physician and dispensing pharmacist, drug name, dosage, formulation, quantity dispensed, date and duration of the dispensation for publicly insured people.

Data management and sharing

Province-specific cohorts will use standardized algorithms to determine crucial data, which have all already been developed by the existing team in Quebec. All linkages will be done by denormalized unique identifiers for mothers/children (the mother-child link is ensured by a unique mother-baby link already available in each province). As mentioned before, the team will follow the EU CONSIGN protocol concerning medication definitions, diagnosis codes and some of the analyses. CAMCCO harmonizes provincial cohorts and crude data cannot leave the province. Thus, only aggregated data will be shared.

2.2. Case-based databases on pregnancy and COVID-19

Eligible for inclusion are cohorts or registries collecting data on pregnant women identified in antenatal care of health care facilities with a positive for SARS-CoV-2 at any point during pregnancy using RT-PCR between January 1, 2020, and December 31, 2020, and at least follow-up until two days after delivery. These registries should have qualitative information available on inpatient medicines used around the COVID-19 positive period or test and maternal and perinatal outcomes. Data collections on self-reported pregnancies are not included because of the risk of selection and misclassification. The

identified cohorts/registries that agreed to participate in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Overview of participating initiatives/organizations based on case-based databases

Study / network name	Countries	Type of data source	Contact persons
COVI-PREG CONSIGN WP2 (EMA)	22 countries, with Switzerland, France and Spain including most patients	Registry	Alice Panchaud Guillame Favre Emeline Maisonneuve
INOSS CONSIGN WP3 (EMA)	Multiple EU countries participating in the INOSS network	Population-based registry	Kitty Bloemenkamp Hilde Engjom Odette de Bruin
SET-NET (CDC)	USA	Population-based registry	Suzanne Gilboa Kate Woodworth
George Washington Meta-analysis	21 countries across the world	Prospective meta-analysis	Emily Smith Erin Oakley
SFDA	Saudi-Arabia	Retrospective, multi-database, dynamic cohort study	Nouf S. Al-Fadel

2.2.1. COVI-PREG CONSIGN WP2 (EMA)

COVI-PREG is a registry of all women suspected having COVID-19 disease during pregnancy and visited a participating antenatal health clinic. The purpose of COVI-PREG is:

- To launch a prospective structured data collection to allow future research projects leading to a better characterization of the risks associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection in pregnancy.
- To create a responsive data collection system through a health care facilities network to ensure a rapid assessment of the risks linked to future emergent pathogens.

The global network which was established as part of the Zika investigations and has been repurposed for COVID-19 is described in a publication by Panchaud et al.²⁷

Data from participating sites is collected in a REDCAP repository coordinated and maintained by the University of Lausanne in Switzerland. In the final analysis, a total of 1964 pregnant women, from 35 countries across the world, were included. These pregnant women had a positive SARS-CoV-2 test between March 25th, 2020, and June 1st, 2021.⁴

Data collection

The codebook was shared and mapped to the other initiatives described in this section. Data collection includes:

- Enrolment: Baseline demographics: age, marital status, ethnicity, education, country of residence, region of residence
- SARS-CoV-2 maternal testing: date performed, result, other tests performed (influenza, respiratory syncytial virus)
- Ongoing pregnancy information: date of last menstrual period, gestational age at enrolment, gravidity, parity, multiple gestation, first trimester screening date and results

- Maternal comorbidities: obesity, diabetes (pre-gestational, gestational with or without medicine), thyroid function imbalances, hypertension, coronary heart disease, chronic obstructive lung disease, other illnesses
- Maternal addictions: alcohol, tobacco, recreational drug used during pregnancy
- Maternal medicines
- Maternal serological and immunization status when available at enrolment: toxoplasmosis, cytomegalovirus, varicella zoster virus, herpes simplex virus, rubella, syphilis, HIV, hepatitis C, hepatitis B, lymphocytic choriomeningitis virus, influenza vaccine, pertussis vaccine
- Maternal and fetal genetic testing when available at enrolment: trisomy 21 screening, non-invasive prenatal testing (i.e., analysis of fetal DNA in maternal blood), invasive genetic testing performed in some cases (amniocentesis, chorionic villus sampling)
- Follow-up: SARS - CoV-2 testing on amniotic fluid testing when it was performed for genetic purposes (date performed, result), placenta testing (date performed, result), products of fetal loss if applicable (date performed, result), new-born testing (date performed, result), human milk (date performed, result)
- Maternal outcomes: abnormal lab result (thrombocytopenia, lymphocytopenia, anemia, C-reactive protein, lactate dehydrogenase U/L (>245), ALT, U/L (>40))
- Lung Imaging: X-ray, CT scan, MRI (Date, result)
- COVID-19 medicines: antiviral (name, duration, timing before delivery), antibiotic (name, duration), corticosteroids (name, duration, timing before delivery), chloroquine (yes, no, duration, timing before delivery), intravenous immunoglobulin (name, duration, timing before delivery)
- Hospital admission related to COVID-19 (yes, no, duration, time from illness onset), high-flow nasal cannula oxygen therapy (yes, no, duration, time from illness onset), ICU admission (yes, no, duration, time from illness onset), noninvasive mechanical ventilation (yes, no, duration, time from illness onset), invasive mechanical ventilation (yes, no, duration, time from illness onset), ECMO (duration, time from illness onset), renal replacement therapy ((yes, no, duration, time from illness onset)
- Complication: sepsis, respiratory failure, acute respiratory distress syndrome, heart failure, septic shock, coagulopathy, renal failure, and disseminated intravascular coagulopathy, others
- Pregnancy outcomes: multiple gestation, pregnancy termination (elective or spontaneous), stillbirth, preterm
- Prenatal imaging: dating ultrasound results and measurements, subsequent ultrasound results and measurements, if abnormal: IUGR type, anomalies (description)
- Infant outcomes: gestational age at delivery, mode of delivery, sex, weight, height, occipitofrontal circumference, APGAR scores, umbilical arterial and venous blood pH, physical examination (if abnormal, neurological exam, splenomegaly, hepatomegaly, congenital malformation, NICU admission, feeding method and other immediate outcomes). Imaging and further investigations: blood count results, screening for other infectious diseases, magnetic resonance imaging, other abnormalities
- Early neurodevelopmental outcomes: mothers will provide information on their child's development at 6,12 and 24 months of age using the Ages and Stages Questionnaire (third edition) scores for communication, motor, problem solving, social development and child health outcomes.

Data management and sharing

For the meta-analysis, an R script will be developed to allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

2.2.2. INOSS CONSIGN WP3 (EMA)

The International Network of Obstetric Survey Systems (INOSS) is a multi-country collaboration formed to facilitate studies of uncommon and severe complications of pregnancy and childbirth. Collaborations such as INOSS offer many benefits in the study of rare complications. The use of uniform case definitions, common datasets, specifically collected detailed data and prospectively agreed comparative and combined analysis all add to the validity of studies and their utility to guide policy and clinical practice and hence improve the quality of care. Such multi-national collaborations allow for the conduct of robust studies less subject to many of the biases attributed to typical observational studies. For very rare conditions such collaborations may provide the only route to providing high quality evidence to guide practice.²⁸

Data collection

At the moment, population-based data on medicines and COVID-19 in pregnancy is available in the UK, The Netherlands, Belgium, Nordic countries (Denmark, Sweden, Iceland, Norway, Finland), Italy, and potentially will be available for France, Slovakia, and Catalonia region in Spain.

In INOSS, COVID-19 data is collected in a standardized manner using the CRF that has been defined at the start of the pandemic by UKOSS. Any woman admitted to hospital (as an inpatient of ambulatory care) with confirmed COVID-19 infection in pregnancy is eligible. Data are retrieved from clinical records with continuous documentation of treatment during admission, and data collection completed at the end of pregnancy with follow-up until discharge following the end of pregnancy.

The codebook is shared and is being mapped to the other initiatives. Data collection includes:

- Baseline data: age, marital status, ethnicity, country of residence, employment, height weight, smoking
- Previous medical history: asthma, hypertension, diabetes, other comorbidities
- Pregnancy information: estimated date of delivery, gravidity, prior problematic pregnancies, parity, multiple gestation, hospitalization, current pregnancy problems (pregnancy induced hypertension, eclampsia, gestational diabetes)
- Diagnosis of COVID-19: symptoms, virological tests, imaging, source contact
- Treatments in hospital: antiviral medicines, other medicines, steroids for fetal lung maturation, ECMO, SARS - CoV-2 testing
- Pregnancies outcomes: miscarriage, termination of pregnancy, stillbirth, livebirth, gestational age at delivery
- Mode of delivery: induction of labor, vaginal birth, emergency or planned caesarean section
- Maternal outcomes: level 3 critical care, major maternal morbidity, ICU admission, death
- Infant outcomes: gestational age at delivery, mode of delivery, sex, weight, height, APGAR score at 5 min, neonatal ward admission, COVID-19, congenital anomalies, death prior to discharge.

Data management and sharing

For the meta-analysis, an R script will be proposed that will allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables. Most of the INOSS countries have so far stated that they prefer to do analyses without script. It may also be a challenge for them to import such external scripts to institutional safe server databases. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

2.2.3. SET-NET (CDC)

Surveillance for Emerging Threats to Mothers and Babies network collects information on pregnant women and their children through the first 3 years of life.²⁹ This system aims to determine how health threats, such as COVID-19, hepatitis C, syphilis, and Zika, affect these populations. It may also track congenital anomalies, developmental problems, and other disabilities. SET-NET data comes from case report forms, birth certificates, and medical record review.

CDC scientists use these data to:

- Monitor and improve the health of pregnant women and infants.
- Link families to medical and social services to get recommended care.
- Strengthen laboratory and clinical testing to find emerging health threats quickly.
- Ensure public health departments are ready and prepared to meet the needs of pregnant women and infants during emergencies.

This surveillance builds upon the US Zika Pregnancy and Infant Registry. A key part of this unique surveillance is finding exposures during pregnancy and linking them with health outcomes of pregnant women and infants.

Data on laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 cases³⁰ are electronically reported to CDC using a standardized case report form³¹ or National Notifiable Diseases Surveillance System (NNDSS)³² as part of COVID-19 surveillance efforts. Data are reported by health departments and can be updated by health departments as the latest information becomes available. Information on demographic characteristics, pregnancy status, underlying medical conditions, symptoms, and outcomes is collected. Pregnancy status is ascertained by a pregnancy field on the COVID-19 case report form or through records linked to the Surveillance for Emerging Threats to Mothers and Babies Network (SET-NET) optional COVID-19 module. Data up to 4 treatments of COVID-19 is collected in SET-NET, but not in the COVID-19 case report form. Remdesivir is collected as a unique variable, and three free text fields collect additional treatments. Abstractors are referred to the National Institutes of Health for COVID-19 treatments. Additional non-specific treatments (e.g., antibiotics, bronchodilators, antipyretics) may not be systematically captured.

As of December 2021, 47,428 pregnant women with SARS-CoV-2 infection in 2020 have been reported to SET-NET.³³

Data collection

Maternal outcomes of interest are:

- In hospital maternal mortality: all-cause mortality, COVID-19 specific mortality
- Morbidity outcomes: COVID-19 related clinical signs and symptoms, maternal disease severity,³⁴ pregnancy-related complications (hypertensive disease including pre-eclampsia/eclampsia, gestational diabetes)
- Other morbidity-related outcomes: hospitalization, admittance to an intensive care unit, requiring intensive ventilation
- Adverse pregnancy outcomes: stillbirth, preterm birth, early pregnancy losses (<20 weeks)

Neonatal outcomes of interest include:

- Neonatal SARS-CoV-2 testing results from birth hospitalizations (up to 14 days of life)
- Neonatal Intensive Care Unit admission
- Birth defects (through ICD-10 codes)
- Neonatal death
- Preterm birth
- Low birth weight
- Small-for-gestational age

Data management and sharing

For the meta-analysis, an R script will be developed that will allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

2.2.4. George Washington Meta-analysis

Smith et al.³⁵ are conducting a large prospective meta-analysis to study the impact of COVID-19 on pregnancy outcomes. Through a wide search, 19 studies taking place in 21 countries were identified that prospectively agreed to pool data for this analysis (Table 7). Among these 19 prospectively included studies, ten are COVID-19 registry studies, seven are cohort or surveillance studies, and two are case-control studies. More than 74,000 pregnant women are expected to contribute to the completed analysis. Table 7 also shows the eligibility of the studies for the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis. This is based on a preliminary review of the study protocol and may change when studies are reviewed more thoroughly.

Data collection

According to their published protocol, maternal outcomes of interest are:

- Mortality outcomes: all-cause mortality, COVID-19 specific mortality and pregnancy-related mortality

- Morbidity outcomes: COVID-19 related clinical signs and symptoms (fever, cough, shortness of breath, dizziness or fainting, body aches, runny nose, sore throat, loss of sense of smell, loss of sense of taste, sneezing, fatigue, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, headache), pregnancy-related clinical signs and symptoms (hypertensive disease including pre-eclampsia/eclampsia, hyperemesis, intrauterine growth restriction, abnormal placentation, placental abruption, preterm labor, preterm rupture of membranes, hemorrhage, embolic disease, anesthetic complications)
- Other morbidity-related outcomes: hospitalization, admittance to an intensive care unit, requiring critical care, requiring intensive ventilation
- Adverse pregnancy outcomes: stillbirth, early preterm birth, preterm birth, small-for-gestational-age birth, low birth weight
- SARS-CoV-2 viral load: amniotic fluid, placenta, cord blood, vaginal swab, faces, rectal swab, nasopharyngeal swab, pregnancy tissue in the case of fetal demise or induces abortion, breastmilk, maternal blood

Neonatal outcomes of interest include:

- Congenital anomalies (neural tube defects, microcephaly, congenital malformations of ear, congenital heart defects, orofacial clefts, congenital malformations of digestive system, congenital malformations of genital organs, abdominal wall defects, chromosomal abnormalities, reduction defects of upper and lower limbs, talipes equinovarus/clubfoot)
- NICU admission at birth
- Neonatal death: early neonatal (7 days), neonatal (28 days), and six-week infant mortality (42 days), perinatal death (stillbirth or early neonatal death)
- Mother to child transmission of SARS-CoV-2 (intrauterine versus intrapartum or early peripartum infection)

Data management and sharing

For the meta-analysis, an R script will be developed that will allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

2.2.5. Saudi CONSIGN (S-FDA)

The Saudi Food & Drug Authority made a protocol on COVID-19 in pregnancy and medicine use based on the CONSIGN Project. They are conducting a retrospective, multi-database, dynamic cohort study, and are retrieving all data from 2018-2021 including a period of SARS-CoV-2 circulation in Saudi Arabia until the date of the last data availability for the data source. The data provided from pregnant followed up at 2 maternity hospitals representative of the general population: one university hospital and one national hospital.

Participants for this study are women of reproductive age, pregnant women and their new-borns observed in one of the participating data sources for at least one day during the study period and are identified from hospital system through review medical and pharmacy records.

Table 7. Overview of studies that have agreed to participate in the meta-analysis by Smith et al. and their eligibility for the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis

Name of Study	Lead investigators	Country	Design	Outcomes	Expected numbers	Eligible for CONSIGN-International
ANCOV (ARC Kenya)	V. Akelo B.T. Barr D. Onyango	Kenya (Kisumu)	Prospective cohort study (all pregnancies)	Maternal	2500	Yes
PRIORITY USA ³⁶	S. Gaw V. Flaherman, V. Jacoby Y. Afshar	USA	Registry (cases only), self-reporting	Maternal Neonatal (12 months)	1500	No, self-reporting registry
Madrid Hospital-based registry	M. Gil I. Fernandez Buhigas	Spain (Madrid)	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	54	Yes
GESTACOVID Chile ³⁷	O. Hernandez J. Carrillo	Chile	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	1200	Yes
UKOSS ³⁸	M. Knight	UK	Prospective cohort study (all pregnancies), population-based	Maternal	1700	Yes, but already included in INOSS CONSIGN WP3
Neonatal complications study ³⁹	C. Gale J. Kurinczuk	UK	Prospective cohort study (all neonates), neonatal outcomes of pregnant cases identified by UKOSS study	Neonatal	500	Yes, but already included in INOSS CONSIGN WP3
CCV Mali	K. Kotloff	Mali	Two prospective cohorts (all pregnancies) and two case-control	Maternal Neonatal (6 months)	2000/ 1000/ 1500/ 7500	Yes
PERICOVID ⁴⁰	K. Le Doare P. von Dadelszen	Uganda Malawi The Gambia Mozambique Kenya	Prospective cohort study (all pregnancies)	Maternal Neonatal (6 wks)	10.000	Yes
Mexico National Registry ⁴¹	Martinez-Portilla	Mexico	Registry (cases only)	?	5249	Yes
NICHD Global Network ⁴²	B. McClure	Bangladesh Kenya Guatemala DRC India Pakistan Zambia USA	Prospective cohort (all pregnancies)	Maternal Neonatal	16.000	Yes
NICHD MFMU network ⁴³	T. Metz R. Clifton	USA	Registry and prospective cohort (all pregnancies)	Maternal	2000	Yes
CANCOVID-Preg Canada ⁴⁴	D. Money	Canada	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	1000	Yes
China COVID Registry	L. Poon	China	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	125	Yes
Hong Kong COVID Registry	H. Yang	Hong Kong	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal		Yes
RECOGEST Colombia ⁴⁵	J. Sanin N. Velasquez J. Tolosa	Colombia	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	400	Yes
Washington state COVID-19	K.A. Waldorf E. Lokken	35 hospitals Washington State	Retrospective registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	240	Yes
CHOPAN ⁴⁶	C. Whitehead	Australia & New Zealand	Registry (cases only)	Maternal Neonatal	100	Yes

The objectives of Saudi CONSIGN are:

1. To estimate the prevalence of medication used to treat pregnant women with acute COVID-19 infection
2. To estimate the prevalence of medication used to treat COVID-19 infection complications among pregnant women
3. To estimate the prevalence of medication used chronically by pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 infection
4. To evaluate the maternal outcome of pregnancy in women with COVID-19
5. To evaluate the rate of fetal complication among women diagnosed with COVID-19 infection
6. To evaluate the neonatal outcome for pregnant women diagnosed with COVID-19 infection

Data collection

They are collecting the following variables:

- Demographic maternal: age, weight, BMI
- Hospitalization status: due to COVID-19, due to obstetric reason (with or without COVID-19)
- Maternal outcomes: trimester, gravidity, parity, smoking (y/n), gestational age at time for delivery (week + day), delivery type (spontaneous, induced, c-section), comorbidities (DM, HTN, pulmonary, mental health disorder, cardiovascular, rheumatoid arthritis, history of cancer, history of liver or renal disorders, obesity, fetal growth restriction, previous abortion, previous malformation, previous stillbirth)
- Maternal COVID-19 severity status: any recorded diagnosis (level 1), confirmed hospitalized (level 2), ICU admission due to COVID-19 (level 3), ARDS (level 4), death (level 5)
- Pregnancy complication: abnormal placentation, gestational DM, gestational HTN, termination of pregnancy due to fetal anomaly, other
- Intrapartum and postpartum maternal complication: congenital anomalies, transferred to ICU, haemorrhage, death, other
- Maternal medication history: chronic medications (antihypertensive, antidiabetics, inhalers, analgesics, steroids, anticoagulants, antiplatelets, antimicrobials, topical antimicrobial, immunosuppressants, antipsychotics, multivitamins, folic acid, cough products), acute for COVID-19 infection (ascorbic acid, zinc sulphate, multivitamin, therapeutic anticoagulant, prophylactic anticoagulant, antibiotics, inhalers, cough syrup, dexamethasone, diuretics, antihypertensive, dialysis, ECMO, antivirals), post-COVID-19 infection (therapeutic anticoagulation, antibiotics, dexamethasone, inhalers, multivitamins, cough syrup, home oxygen, continue on dialysis)
- Neonatal outcomes: birth weight, microcephaly, preterm birth, IUGR, stillbirth, infection, Apgar score, transferred to NICU, death

Data management and sharing

For the meta-analysis, an R script will be developed that will allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

3. Proposed approaches and next steps forward

CONSIGN-International will conduct two meta-analyses, one based on secondary use of health care data, and one based on primary data collected in COVID-19 and pregnancies registries or cohorts.

3.1. Most important variables of interest

Tables 8 and 9 display the most important variables of interest that will be used in both analyses:

- Study Population: in and outpatients and the period of data covered
- With or without COVID-19 diagnosis (PCR test)
- Stratification on the severity will distinguish 2 levels for the meta-analysis on healthcare databases:
 - Non-severe: any recorded diagnosis without a hospitalization for COVID-19
 - Severe: any recorded diagnosis AND hospitalization for COVID-19
- Stratification according to the severity will distinguish 3 levels for the meta-analysis on case-based data sources:
 - Level 1: any recorded diagnosis
 - Level 2: hospitalization for COVID-19
 - Level 3: ICU admission for COVID-19 and/or acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation (ARDS) during hospitalization for COVID-19
- Exposure: medication used to treat COVID-19
- Outcomes: maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes
- Potential inclusion biases identified

Table 8. Description of the main variables of interest for the meta-analysis on EHR databases

Data source	Expected number of pregnant women with COVID-19	Period of data covered	In/outpatients	Medicines	Outcomes	Potential inclusion biases
CONSIGN WP1	2022	From March 1 st , 2020 – between June 30 and March 31, 2021, according to DAPs	Out	ATC-level 2 Dispensing or prescribing date considered as timing of medication use	Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes	>30% of the women were aged >35; 26.7% as at-risk of developing severe COVID-19; outpatients, less 1 st trimesters
Sentinel system (FDA- Harvard Pilgrim)	Approximately 10000	From Jan 1, 2020-present (lag time varies by Data Partner, currently about 3-5 months)	In + out	Outpatient pharmacy claims using National Drug Codes (NDC)	Maternal, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes	Only live births, publicly insured people may be underrepresented, and uninsured people are not represented
CAMCCO	5780 (approximative estimation considering 1.7% of COVID positive pregnant women and the number of births provided in table 5)	1996-2021	In + out	ATC-level 2 (+/- ATC-level 5) Medical and Pharmacy Insurance Claims – outpatient and inpatient calendar date, name of drug (DIN), dosage, duration	Maternal, Pregnancy, neonatal	No bias detected so far

Table 9. Description of the main variables of interest for the meta-analysis on registries databases

Data source	Expected number of pregnant women with COVID-19	Period of data covered	In/out patients	Medicines	Outcomes	Potential inclusion biases
COVI-PREG, WP2	2700	March 25, 2020 December 2021	In + out	All with date before delivery	Maternal, Pregnancy, neonatal	More severe cases, more comorbidities, less 1 st trimesters
INOSS	+/- 10000	Feb, 2020 – Dec 2020	In	All during hospital admission	Maternal, Pregnancy, Neonatal	No bias detected so far
SET-NET (CDC)	47000 pregnant women with COVID-19 in 2020	From January 1 st , 2020 – Dec 31, 2021	In + out	Remdesivir, other COVID-19 medication	Maternal, Pregnancy, neonatal	No bias detected so far
George Washington MA	53068 - 2200 already included in INOSS CONSIGN WP3 = 50'868	Begin pandemic - ongoing	In + out	Depending on data source	Maternal, Pregnancy, Neonatal	No bias detected so far
S-FDA	2200	March 2020 to October 2021	In + out	Chronic medication, medication acute for COVID-19 and post COVID-19 infection medication	Maternal, Pregnancy, Neonatal	No bias detected so far

3.2. Proposed approaches meta-analysis on EHR databases

Method/design

Data access providers could use the CONSIGN WP1 protocol, or parts of it. The CONSIGN research team will provide a codebook with all the variables to be used for the meta-analysis. The participating organizations may use the ConcepTION CDM and common analytics may be utilized. Cross-mapping of Sentinel and CAMMCCO common data models to ConcepTION CDM structure can be conducted such that CONSIGN R-scripts can be utilized directly or data sources can program themselves. Aggregated results will be collected and stored on the secure Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

Analysis

In the first stage, a summary statistic will be calculated for each study, to describe the prevalence of medicines in pregnant women with COVID-19, pregnant women without COVID-19; and non-pregnant women of reproductive age with COVID-19; the severity and clinical outcomes of COVID-19 disease in pregnant women with COVID-19 and in non-pregnant women of reproductive age with COVID-19, and observe the effect of COVID-19 medication on maternal, pregnancy and perinatal outcomes in the same way for every study.

In the second stage, a summary (combined) effect of COVID-19 medication estimate will be calculated as a weighted average of the intervention effects estimated in the individual studies. A random-effect model will be used.

3.3. Proposed approaches meta-analysis on registry databases

Method/design

The CONSIGN team will provide a codebook with all the variables to be used for the meta-analysis. Data is collected locally, and collaborators will be asked to transfer the data locally in a structurally and semantically harmonized data set. Also, an R script will be developed and provided that will allow for harmonized analysis across all the initiatives, based on a common data model of variables. Only aggregated results will be shared and uploaded to the Digital Research Environment for further pooling.

Analysis

In the first stage, a summary statistic will be calculated for each study, to describe the prevalence of medicines in pregnant women with COVID-19, clinical outcomes of COVID-19 disease in pregnant women with COVID-19 and observe the effect of COVID-19 medication on maternal, pregnancy and perinatal outcomes in the same way for every study.

In the second stage, a summary (combined) effect of COVID-19 medication estimate will be calculated as a weighted average of the intervention effects estimated in the individual studies. A random-effect model will be used.

3.4 Next steps and timeline

Next steps

- Meetings with the participating organizations will be organized to discuss the definitions of variables
- Creating a codebook
- Writing a meta-analysis protocol statistical analysis plan

See also Figure 2 for the next phases in the CONSIGN-International meta-analysis.

Timeline

- 16 January 2022: **Deliverable 6:** Description and characterization of the data sources to be included in the meta-analysis
- February 2022: A common Code Book will be shared with all the participating DAPs.
- 16 March 2022: **Deliverable 7:** Meta-analysis protocol and study analysis plan
- 16 December 2022: **Deliverable 8:** Report and manuscript including final results of the meta-analysis

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